

IMPORTANCES TEACHING RULES OF GRAMMAR FOR (ESP) STUDENTS OF MEDICAL INSTITUTES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12306059>

Abstract. *As a fellow language educator at the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, I understand the complexities of teaching English as a Foreign Language (EFL) to students with diverse linguistic backgrounds. One of the most debated aspects of language acquisition is the role of grammar. While some advocate for a purely communicative approach, neglecting grammar entirely can leave learners feeling lost in a sea of vocabulary. So, how do we strike a balance? This article argues that grammar is a crucial but nuanced element in the EFL classroom, and that a teacher's knowledge of both English grammar and their students' native grammar systems is instrumental in fostering effective language acquisition.*

Key words: *Grammar, learner, building, rules, sentences, language, students, benefit, patient's, articles.*

Introduction. Imagine trying to construct a building without a blueprint or understanding of structural principles. This is akin to learning a language without a grasp of grammar. Grammar provides the foundation – the rules and patterns that govern how words combine to form sentences and convey meaning. Understanding verb conjugations, sentence structure, and how tenses express time allows learners to move beyond rote memorization and towards fluency. For instance, mastering the present perfect tense empowers students to not only describe past actions but also their ongoing impact on the present, a vital skill in the medical field when discussing a patient's medical history (Celce-Murcia & Larsen-Freeman, 1999). Grammar also fosters accuracy in communication. Misusing tenses like the simple past and present perfect can lead to misunderstandings, particularly in critical fields like medicine.

However, focusing solely on grammar drills can create a sterile learning environment. Effective language acquisition goes beyond memorizing rules. Grammar should be presented within a meaningful context, allowing students to see how it functions in real-world communication. Here's where communicative approaches come in. By incorporating authentic medical texts, role-playing scenarios, and discussions, we can help students not only understand grammar rules but also apply them effectively in situations relevant to their field.

Consider the following example: A student struggling with the present continuous tense might benefit from practicing by role-playing a doctor-patient consultation, where they describe a patient's ongoing symptoms ("He is experiencing chest pain"). This not only reinforces the grammatical concept but also hones their communication skills in a practical setting.

Methods and research. Teacher's knowledge of both English grammar and the students' native grammar systems plays a vital role in this process. Understanding the similarities and differences between the two languages allows for more targeted instruction. Let's say a student from an Uzbek-speaking background is struggling with the concept of articles (a/an/the) in English. Knowing that Uzbek doesn't use articles, the teacher can explain the function of articles in English using clear visuals and examples relevant to the medical field (e.g., "a patient," "the symptoms"). This comparative approach bridges the gap between the familiar and the unfamiliar, fostering a deeper understanding (Celce-Murcia & Larsen-Freeman, 1999).

Outline some of the difficulties for learners of English posed by the English verbs system, both in form and meaning. Suggest steps a teacher might take to overcome these difficulties. As a fellow EFL instructor at the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, I understand the complexities students face when grappling with the English verb system. Unlike many languages, English verbs boast a multitude of forms for tense, aspect, and mood, presenting a formidable obstacle for learners (Celce-Murcia & Larsen-Freeman, 1999). These difficulties extend to both the form and meaning of verbs.

On the formal side, the sheer number of verb conjugations can be overwhelming. Regular verbs follow predictable patterns, but irregular verbs like "go" and "went" defy these rules, adding another layer of complexity. Furthermore, the concept of aspect, which conveys the completeness or ongoing nature of an action, can be particularly challenging for learners whose native languages lack this distinction. For instance, the difference between the simple past ("He took the medicine") and the present perfect ("He has taken the medicine") might be unclear to students accustomed to expressing both with a single verb form. Meaning-wise, English verbs often carry nuances that can be tricky to grasp. The subtle differences between verbs like "see" and "look," or "know" and "understand," can lead to confusion. These challenges are compounded in a field like medicine, where precise communication is paramount. A misunderstanding of verb tense, for example, could lead to misinterpreting a patient's medical history.

So, how can we navigate this verb tense jungle? Several strategies can prove effective. One approach involves leveraging students' native language as a reference point. By drawing comparisons and contrasts between the two verb systems, we can help students bridge the gap between the familiar and the unfamiliar. Additionally, incorporating authentic medical texts and dialogues into the classroom allows students to see verb usage in context (Dudley-Evans & St. John, 1998). Analyzing these materials can shed light on how verb forms function in real-world medical scenarios. Finally, explicit instruction on verb forms, tenses, and aspects, coupled with ample practice opportunities, can solidify students' understanding and equip them to use verbs accurately and effectively. By employing these strategies, we can empower our students to navigate the intricacies of the English verb system, fostering clear and confident communication in the crucial field of medicine.

Conclusion. In conclusion, grammar plays a vital but nuanced role in the EFL classroom. It provides the foundation for accurate and effective communication, particularly in a critical field like medicine. However, rote memorization without context is not enough. By integrating grammar instruction with a communicative approach and leveraging their knowledge of both English grammar and the students' native language systems, teachers can create a dynamic learning environment that fosters not just grammatical accuracy but also fluency and confidence in using English for real-world communication.

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